

A NUMERICAL MODEL FOR COUPLING HYGRO-MECHANICAL PHENOMENA IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the numerical development of the coupled hygro-mechanical behavior of composite materials. Indeed, it is shown by experimental studies that the moisture content has an influence on the mechanical properties of composite materials [1]. The studied material shows a Fickian diffusion process so that a Fick's law characterized by the diffusion matrix \mathbf{D} will be employed to describe the spatio-temporal variation of the local moisture content. The diffusion or diffusivity matrix is defined as a diagonal matrix containing the diffusion coefficients in each spatial direction. The mechanical behavior is modeled with a hygro-elastic law which means that in addition to the elastic strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e(\mathbf{x}, t)$, the moisture absorption will induce a strain which is assumed to be linearly proportional to the moisture content, i.e. $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^h(\mathbf{x}, t) = \boldsymbol{\beta}^h c(\mathbf{x}, t)$ where $\boldsymbol{\beta}^h$ is the hygroscopic expansion matrix [2]. The elasticity matrix \mathbb{C} is considered to belong to the transverse isotropic class of material symmetry. The proposed diffusion and mechanical coupling is based on the evolution of the coefficients of the elasticity matrix as a function of the average moisture content in the composite material. This function is considered as linear in this study and can be straightforwardly extended to the case of more complex functions. Within the framework of a linear evolution of elastic coefficients, this evolution function only requires the elastic coefficients in the initial state (unaged composite) and the those in the final state (aged composite attained its water absorption capacity). Therefore, the resulting stress-strain curve will therefore be piecewise linear and hence nonlinear overall.

To take into account the evolution of the mechanical properties, we developed a particular 3D element whose stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{K}]$ includes the contribution of both mechanical and diffusion phenomena. This matrix is fully expressed in terms of the finite element shape functions. Implementation of this 3D element is done within an Abaqus user element (UEL) subroutine written in Fortran language.

1 INTRODUCTION

Using composite materials especially in the domain of Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) is a research topic that aims at improving the mechanical and environmental performances along with the lightening of structures. However, since the water diffusion can have negative impacts on the mechanical performance of the structure, the long-term behavior of these materials subjected to harsh environments should be a major concern. For instance, water diffusion through a composite material can generate hygroscopic stresses that may exceed its ultimate tensile strength without any applied mechanical loading.

The water absorbs through the submerged surfaces of a composite material with porosity inside. Then, it spreads through its volume following some diffusion mechanism that is characterized by a diffusion

equation. The solution of the diffusion equation gives a so-called sorption curve which is the temporal variation of the normalized mass uptake resulting from the water diffusion. This curve specifies the kinetics of diffusion in the material under study. Theoretical formulation of the diffusion process and humid aging has been a research subject since the last three decades [2, 3]. In the corresponding literature, one can find some diffusion models such as the Fick, two-stage Fick and Langmuir [6, 7]. Among these models, Fick's law that is analogous to the Fourier law for the heat equation, is extensively used especially for the polymers and composites [4, 5]. In this paper, we will focus only on materials that are governed by the Fick's diffusion law or the so-called Fickian materials.

Several experimental studies on composite materials, reported a decrease, on the one hand, in their elastic moduli and, on the other hand, in their ultimate tensile and shear strengths [8, 9]. From these observations, it has been found that the mechanical properties are decreasing functions of the local moisture content at any point of the material. For instance, the experimental studies of Tual et al. [1] revealed important drops on shear modulus and the ultimate strengths in terms of the immersion time. As such, it is of major importance to properly estimate the impacts of the diffusion process on the long-term mechanical behavior of the composite materials. For this purpose, there are many numerical works on the coupling of mechanical and diffusion phenomena [10, 11].

In this paper, a simple approach which could be of industrial importance, is numerically implemented to model the coupling between the diffusion and mechanical behaviors of a composite material. This pragmatic approach considers a linear model to describe the variation of the components of the elasticity matrix as a function of the local moisture content. The main advantage of this model is that it is a linear model and thus it takes into account only the values of the corresponding parameters at the initial (unaged) and final (aged) states. This model is implemented via a user defined element (UEL) subroutine in Abaqus software.

2 DIFFUSION AND MECHANICAL MODELING

The analysis of the experimental data that we have at our disposal from the diffusion study (immersed specimens in water to follow their aging) shows a Fickian-type evolution. The three-dimensional Fick's law is used to model the diffusion process:

$$\frac{\partial c(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} = D_x \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2} + D_y \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial y^2} + D_z \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial z^2} \quad (\mathbf{x}, t) \in \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (1)$$

in which c denotes the moisture content over the medium $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^3$ at each time t , and D_x , D_y and D_z specify the diffusion constants following each space direction.

A linear elastic constitutive law considering the hygroscopic strain generated by the diffusion process, models the mechanical state of the system:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t) - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^h(\mathbf{x}, t)) \quad (2)$$

In which \mathbf{C} is the fourth-rank elasticity tensor that depends a priori on the local moisture content at each point of the material, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^h$ is the hygroscopic strain.

3 LINEAR MODEL FOR HYGROMECHANICAL COUPLING

By observing the experimental results obtained by Nicolas Tual [1] (Fig. 1), it is possible to propose a function of evolution of the shear modulus and resistances. This function could be either a linear or non-linear (for instance a polynomial approximation) evolution. In this paper, we propose to model

different evolutions of mechanical properties as a function of the moisture content by a linear approximation because it has the advantage of requiring only the properties in the initial state (unaged specimen) and the properties in the final state. The final state here implies that the specimen reached its capacity of water absorption which corresponds to the plateau of the sorption curve resulting from the Fick's diffusion kinetics. Figure 1 depicts four experimental data showing the variation of the shear modulus during the immersion time. From this figure it implies that the decay occurs in two stages. The first stage (until 40 days of aging) corresponding to the transition phase of the sorption curve in which the decay is significant. Then a second phase during which the specimen almost attained its absorption capacity and the decay rate is much lower. The red line shows the linear approximation of the evolution which should not be confused with a linear regression model that takes into account all the points. Note that this plot could be translated to a variation of the shear modulus in terms of the average moisture content on the entire medium. It should be noted that the hygro-mechanical coupling is taken into account only in one direction. This means that the influence of the mechanical state of the composite material on its diffusion parameters is ignored.

Figure 1: Linear approximation for the shear modulus G_{12} [1]

The linear evolution of the elasticity matrix as a function of the average water content over each element of the numerical finite element scheme \bar{c} is thus considered. As stated above, this model is built based on the mechanical properties of dry material and those of the aged one. Our model then reads:

$$\mathcal{C}(\bar{c}(t)) = \mathcal{C}(c_0) + \left[\frac{\mathcal{C}(c_{\infty}) - \mathcal{C}(c_0)}{c_{\infty}} \right] \bar{c}(t) \quad (3)$$

in which c_{∞} is the maximum moisture absorption capacity of the material c_0 is the initial moisture content, $\mathcal{C}(c_0)$ and $\mathcal{C}(c_{\infty})$ are the elasticity matrices at dry and aged states.

4 NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

4.1 Finite element discretization

The numerical analysis of the hygro-mechanical behavior can be done directly using the Abaqus software via the analogy between the Fick and the heat transfer equations. However, the dependency of the elastic moduli (components of the stiffness matrix) to the moisture content cannot be directly taken into account. For this purpose, we developed an Abaqus User Element (UEL) subroutine allowing us, from one hand to define the elementary finite element stiffness matrix $[K]$ and, on the other hand, to consider any type of variation of the elastic constants in terms of the local moisture.

For the numerical implementation, we consider a linear tetrahedral element characterized by four nodes and one integration (Gauss) point. The finite element shape (interpolation) functions are thus linear. The considered element is isoparametric since the same linear shape functions are used to interpolate the coordinates (geometry) as those used to interpolate the degrees of freedom (dof). At each node we have four dofs (three for displacements in each direction and 1 for the moisture content) and the finite element discretization of the system writes as $[\mathbf{K}]\{\mathbf{u}(t)\} = \{\mathbf{f}(t)\}$. In the latter, $\{\mathbf{u}(t)\}$ and $\{\mathbf{f}(t)\}$ describe respectively the nodal displacement and force at each time t . It can be demonstrated that the 16×16 finite element stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{K}]$ for the diffusion-mechanical behavior reads:

$$[\mathbf{K}] = \begin{bmatrix} [\mathbf{K}_M] & [\mathbf{0}]_{12 \times 4} \\ [\mathbf{0}]_{4 \times 12} & [\mathbf{K}_D] + [\mathbf{M}_D] \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Wherein the 12×12 and 4×4 matrices $[\mathbf{K}_M]$ and $[\mathbf{K}_D]$ correspond respectively the contribution of the mechanical and diffusion behaviors to the total elementary stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{K}]$. Note that the subscripts M and D stand for the mechanical and diffusion phenomena, respectively. The 4×4 matrix $[\mathbf{M}_D]$ could be considered as a mass matrix. These matrices can be obtained by:

$$[\mathbf{K}_M] = \left[\int_{\Omega} [\mathbf{B}_M(\mathbf{x})]^T \mathbf{C}(\bar{c}(t)) [\mathbf{B}_M(\mathbf{x})] d\Omega \right] \quad (5)$$

$$[\mathbf{K}_D] = \left[\int_{\Omega} [\mathbf{B}_D(\mathbf{x})]^T \mathbf{D} [\mathbf{B}_D(\mathbf{x})] d\Omega \right] \quad (6)$$

$$[\mathbf{M}_D] = \left[\frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_{\Omega} [\mathbf{N}_D(\mathbf{x})]^T [\mathbf{N}_D(\mathbf{x})] d\Omega \right] \quad (7)$$

In which the superscript T denotes the transpose operation. In Eq. (5), $[\mathbf{B}_M(\mathbf{x})]$ is the classical strain-displacement matrix. Note that in Eq. (5), the 6×6 elasticity matrix depends on the local water content calculated so that the elementary stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{K}_M]$ is time-dependent during the whole diffusion process. In Eq. (6), the 3×4 matrix $[\mathbf{B}_D(\mathbf{x})]$, similar to $[\mathbf{B}_M(\mathbf{x})]$ relates the gradient of the local moisture content to its nodal values. Furthermore, \mathbf{D} is a 3×3 diagonal matrix containing the diffusion coefficients in each direction, i.e. $\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(D_x, D_y, D_z)$. Finally, in Eq. (7), the 4×4 matrix $[\mathbf{N}_D(\mathbf{x})]$ links the local moisture content to the nodal values. Hence, it is only a function of the finite element interpolation functions. Note also that the matrices $[\mathbf{B}_M(\mathbf{x})]$ and $[\mathbf{B}_D(\mathbf{x})]$ are functions of the spatial derivatives of the shape functions.

4.2 Numerical parameters

The numerical example considered in this section is a 3D linearly elastic composite whose properties are homogenized (upscaled). The elasticity matrix \mathbf{C} is supposed to belong to the transverse isotropic symmetry class. Hence, it could be written in terms of five parameters $E_{11}, E_{22}, G_{12}, \nu_{12}, \nu_{23}$ writes:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{S}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_{11} & -\nu_{12}/E_{11} & -\nu_{12}/E_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_{11} & 1/E_{22} & -\nu_{23}/E_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_{11} & -\nu_{23}/E_{22} & 1/E_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & (1 + \nu_{23})/E_{22} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

Table 1 depicts the experimental results [1] for the initial (unaged) and final (aged) values for the

elastic moduli. It can be observed that the only mechanical parameter that changes during the diffusion process is the shear modulus. Hence, the Poisson's ratios and Young moduli remain unchanged.

Elastic modulus	Unaged Value	Aged Value
E_{11} [MPa]	140000	140000
E_{22} [MPa]	7000	3600
G_{12} [MPa]	3600	2400
ν_{12} [-]	0.32	0.32
ν_{23} [-]	0.40	0.40

Table 1: Elastic coefficients [1]

4.3 Numerical simulations

In this section we exemplify the numerical coupling scheme presented in section 3. For this purpose, a longitudinal tensile test according to the fibers direction (x direction according to Fig. 2) is performed on a cubic immersed specimen. The dimensions of the latter are **100mm × 20mm × 20mm**. As far as the boundary conditions, a displacement of 0.2mm following the x direction is applied to one side of the specimen and the opposite side is blocked (for displacements and rotations).

The medium is discretized using 248348 linear tetrahedral elements resulting in 45610 nodes. The calculation time is 36000000 seconds, or nearly 417 days of immersion of the specimen in water being relatively larger than the immersion times of the experimental results. Figure 2 shows the variation of the displacement field in x direction.

Figure 2: Displacement field induced by the applied boundary conditions.

In order to verify the accuracy of our numerical code, the variations of some elastic constants is plotted during the diffusion process. Figure 3 shows the evolution of the longitudinal Young's modulus E_{11} (constant) and the shear modulus G_{12} (linearly decreasing value) as a function of the water content.

Figure 3: Evolution of the Young E_{11} and G_{12} shear moduli in terms of the water content

The results obtained with the created user element are quite satisfactory when compared with those obtained using the corresponding Abaqus element, i.e. C3D4T (based on a coupled temperature-displacement calculation). For diffusion, the kinetics predicted by the user element and that obtained via the C3D4T element are identical.

Regarding the mechanical behavior, it is noted that there is a difference of about five percent between the longitudinal stresses obtained with the created user element (maximum stress = 338MPa) and the C3D4T element from Abaqus (maximum stress = 320MPa). This difference could be due to the fact that the integrated user element takes into account the evolution of the shear modulus and transverse modulus as a function of the water content.

Figure 4: Distribution of the longitudinal strain ϵ_{11} and stress σ_{11}

In addition, we were able to verify the symmetry of the behavior in the Y and Z directions resulting from the transverse isotropic behavior as it can be seen in Figure 5. The stresses σ_{22} and σ_{33} are approximately equal (the seven percent deviation remains acceptable but probably concerns the maximum values).

Figure 5: Distribution of the transverse stresses σ_{22} and σ_{33}

5 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

In this study, a tetrahedral element was created and numerically integrated as an Abaqus user subroutine (UEL). The element has been formulated to take into account the coupling between the diffusion of water through the composite and its mechanical behavior. The three-dimensional Fick's law is used to model the diffusion process. The mechanical behavior is represented by a linear elastic constitutive behavior considering the stress-free hygroscopic strain generated by the diffusion process with shear and transverse direction properties dependent on water content. Comparison of the results obtained by the created user element with those obtained by a C3D4T Abaqus element shows a good agreement between the results. We believe that this is a pragmatic and practical model for the hygro-mechanical coupling which could be specially of industrial interest.

As a future work, the non-linear evolution of the mechanical properties as a function of the moisture content could be considered. The coupling could also be studied on other parameters, e.g. the absorption capacity or the hygroscopic expansion coefficients.

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